

Impact of Hemodialysis Duration and Clinical Factors on Health-Related Quality of Life in Chronic Kidney Disease Patients

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Received: 2 June 2026
Accepted: 15 June 2026
Published Online: 18 June 2026

Published by:
Gopalganj Medical College, Gopalganj,
Bangladesh

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DOI:

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ABSTRACT

Background: Chronic kidney disease (CKD) progressing to end stage renal disease (ESRD) is an increasing global health burden with high prevalence and significant mortality, including in Bangladesh. In ESRD patients, maintenance hemodialysis is the main life-sustaining therapy that improves survival but imposes a substantial physical and psychosocial burden, thereby reducing health-related quality of life. **Objective:** The aim of the study was to assess the impact of hemodialysis duration and clinical factors on health-related quality of life in chronic kidney disease patients. **Methods & Materials:** This observational cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Nephrology, Shaheed Suhrawardy Medical College Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh, over six months after ethical approval. A total of 100 CKD patients on maintenance hemodialysis were selected by purposive sampling to assess the impact of dialysis duration and clinical factors on health-related quality of life. Data were collected through face-to-face interviews using a structured questionnaire and the validated Bangla SF-36 tool, and analyzed using SPSS version 20.0, with $p < 0.05$ considered significant. **Results:** The study included 100 maintenance hemodialysis patients, mainly aged 61–70 years (33.0%) and male (76.0%). Diabetic nephropathy was the leading cause of CKD (32.0%), and most had serum creatinine 5–7 mg/dl (42.0%). Most patients were on dialysis for 1–5 years (56.0%). SF-36 scores were lowest for general health perception and highest for pain. Longer dialysis duration (>5 years) was significantly associated with lower scores in multiple SF-36 domains ($p < 0.05$). **Conclusion:** Maintenance hemodialysis is associated with significantly impaired quality of life, which progressively worsens with longer treatment duration.

Keywords: Hemodialysis, Chronic Kidney Disease, Health-Related Quality Of Life, SF-36, Clinical Factors.

(The Insight 2026; 9(2): 440-445)

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INTRODUCTION

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) progressing to end stage renal disease (ESRD) has evolved from an occasional clinical condition into a rapidly expanding global health crisis. According to the 2020 Global Burden of Disease study, CKD is responsible for more than 2.6 million deaths worldwide, while projections by the World Health Organization indicate a 41.5% rise in CKD-related mortality by 2040, placing it among the leading ten causes of global death. On a worldwide scale, CKD affects nearly 9–13% of the population and contributes substantially to both illness and death, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) [1]. In Bangladesh, the prevalence is reported at 22.48% [2], exceeding global estimates, and CKD ranked as the 9th leading cause of death in 2018 [3]. Collectively, these findings emphasize CKD as an escalating and major public health challenge both globally and within the local context.

In patients who progress to end-stage renal disease, renal replacement therapies include hemodialysis, peritoneal dialysis, and kidney transplantation, with hemodialysis being

the most commonly utilized modality aimed at maintaining a near-normal functional state for affected individuals [4]. Hemodialysis remains the most frequently applied renal replacement therapy and works by extracorporeal filtration of waste products and excess fluid from the blood [5]. For most individuals reaching ESRD, long-term maintenance hemodialysis becomes the primary life-sustaining treatment. While dialysis significantly improves survival and prolongs life expectancy, it cannot fully substitute the normal functions of healthy kidneys; therefore, treatment goals are directed toward maximizing patient functioning, enhancing overall well-being, and improving quality of life [6].

Although dialysis extends survival, it imposes a considerable burden on patients' daily lives. Renal replacement therapy leads to major lifestyle modifications in individuals with chronic kidney disease [7]. Hemodialysis is a demanding treatment modality that requires regular hospital or dialysis center attendance, typically three sessions per week, resulting in significant disruption of daily activities and routines [8]. Patients frequently experience multiple challenges, including

physical strain and psychological stress, while lifelong dependence on treatment is especially difficult in resource-constrained environments [9]. Long-term survival on dialysis is also associated with a persistent symptom burden such as fatigue, pain, sleep disorders, and psychological distress, all of which collectively contribute to deterioration in health-related quality of life (HRQoL) across physical, psychological, and social domains.

Quality of life represents a broad concept encompassing an individual's physical health, psychological state, level of independence, social relationships, and interaction with their environment, and it may change over time [10]. The World Health Organization defines quality of life as an individual's perception of their position in life in relation to their goals, expectations, standards, and concerns within the cultural and value systems in which they live [11]. In chronic illnesses such as CKD, HRQoL is recognized as a multidimensional construct that includes physical, emotional, mental, and social functioning. Multiple determinants influence HRQoL in CKD patients, including reduced disease control, financial constraints, unemployment, comorbidities such as diabetes mellitus and cardiovascular disease, and treatment-related complications, all of which collectively compromise physical and psychological well-being.

Existing literature has identified dialysis duration as an important factor influencing HRQoL; however, the evidence remains contradictory. Some studies have shown that longer duration of dialysis is associated with a decline in quality of life, with statistically significant relationships [12], whereas others suggest comparatively better quality of life during the initial years of dialysis compared to longer treatment periods. Additionally, multicenter studies have reported both adaptation-related improvement and progressive deterioration over time, leaving the relationship between dialysis duration and HRQoL inconclusive. Nevertheless, many studies conducted in similar settings are limited by small sample sizes, single-center designs, or the absence of validated HRQoL assessment tools, thereby indicating a significant gap in existing evidence, particularly in our context. Chronic kidney disease patients on maintenance hemodialysis experience prolonged treatment exposure that improves survival but may progressively impair physical, psychological, and social well-being. Evidence regarding the effect of dialysis duration and clinical factors on health-related quality of life remains inconsistent, and limited data are available from our local setting using validated instruments such as SF-36. Therefore, this study was conducted to assess the impact of hemodialysis duration and clinical factors on health-related quality of life in chronic kidney disease patients.

OBJECTIVE

To assess the impact of hemodialysis duration and clinical factors on health-related quality of life in chronic kidney disease patients.

METHODS & MATERIALS

This observational cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Nephrology, Shaheed Suhrawardy Medical College Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh, over a period of six months following approval of the study protocol. A total of 100 patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) undergoing maintenance hemodialysis were included in the study using purposive sampling to evaluate the impact of hemodialysis duration and clinical factors on health-related quality of life.

Inclusion Criteria

- All patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) undergoing hemodialysis
- Age >18 years
- Both male and female patients

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients unwilling to provide written informed consent
- Patients with mental disorders
- Patients with decreased level of consciousness

Variables

The main variables of the study were sociodemographic characteristics (age, sex, occupation, education, smoking history), clinical characteristics (cause of CKD, serum creatinine level), duration of maintenance hemodialysis, and health-related quality of life.

No confounding variables were considered in this study.

Data Collection and Organization

A data-capturing master sheet was maintained throughout the study. At enrollment, sociodemographic and clinical characteristics of the patients were recorded. Data were collected through face-to-face interviews using a structured questionnaire focusing on sociodemographic and clinical profiles.

Health-related quality of life was assessed using the Bangla-translated and validated Short Form-36 (SF-36) questionnaire. The SF-36 is a self-administered instrument consisting of 36 items that evaluates health across eight domains of functional status, well-being, and general health perception. Scores are transformed into a scale ranging from 0 (worst health) to 100 (best health).

Data Collection Procedure

Data were collected using a pre-designed pro-forma.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Data were entered into Microsoft Excel (Windows 2010) and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.0. Quantitative variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, while qualitative variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages. Comparison of SF-36 domain scores across duration of hemodialysis groups was performed using appropriate statistical tests, and a p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations

Written approval was obtained from the concerned authority and departmental ethical committee. The study objectives, procedures, risks, and benefits were explained to participants in a locally understandable language. Written informed consent was obtained prior to data collection. Confidentiality, anonymity, and privacy were strictly maintained throughout the study.

RESULTS

Table 1 presents the sociodemographic and clinical characteristics of the study participants. The majority of patients were aged 61–70 years (n = 33, 33.0%), followed by 51–60 years (n = 28, 28.0%). Most participants were male (n = 76, 76.0%). Regarding occupation, business (n = 30, 30.0%) and service (n = 28, 28.0%) were the most common categories. In terms of education, primary level education was most frequent (n = 22, 22.0%). The majority of patients were non-smokers (n = 56, 56.0%). Diabetic nephropathy was the leading cause of CKD (n = 32, 32.0%), and most patients had serum creatinine levels between 5–7 mg/dl (n = 42, 42.0%).

Table I: Sociodemographic and Clinical Characteristics of the Study Population (n = 100).

Variable	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)	21–30	2.0
	31–40	13.0
	41–50	21.0
	51–60	28.0
	61–70	33.0
	>70	3.0
Sex	Male	76.0
	Female	24.0
Profession	Business	30.0
	Service	28.0
	Housewife	20.0
	Cultivation	14.0
	Labour	6.0
	Student	2.0
Education	Illiterate	18.0
	Primary	22.0
	Class V–X	16.0
	SSC	20.0
	HSC	12.0
	Graduate	10.0
	Postgraduate	2.0
Smoking History	Smoker	24.0
	Non-smoker	56.0
	Ex-smoker	20.0
Cause of CKD	Diabetic nephropathy	32.0
	Hypertension	23.0
	Unknown	19.0
	Renovascular disease	11.0
	Obstructive nephropathy	9.0
	Others	6.0
Serum Creatinine (mg/dl)	<5	21.0
	5–7	42.0
	7.1–10	26.0
	>10	11.0

Figure 1: Distribution of Patients According to Duration of Maintenance Hemodialysis (n = 100).

Figure 1 presents the distribution of patients according to duration of maintenance hemodialysis. The majority of patients were on dialysis for 1–5 years (n = 56, 56.0%), followed by 3 months–<1 year (n = 27, 27.0%), and >5 years (n = 17, 17.0%).

Table II presents the SF-36 quality of life scores among hemodialysis patients. The highest mean score was observed in the pain domain (65.56 ± 22.96), while the lowest was in general health perception (25.54 ± 11.52).

Table II: SF-36 Quality of Life Scores Among Hemodialysis Patients (n = 100).

SF-36 Domain	Mean ± SD	Minimum	Maximum
Physical Functioning	49.58 ± 22.98	41	63
Role Limitations due to Physical Problems	27.02 ± 26.56	0	59
Role Limitations due to Emotional Problems	44.15 ± 24.18	38	70
Vitality	38.59 ± 17.47	28	62
Mental Health	51.96 ± 18.56	29	65
Social Functioning	36.79 ± 16.41	18	46
Pain	65.56 ± 22.96	37	98
General Health Perception	25.54 ± 11.52	11	34

Table III compares SF-36 domain scores according to duration of maintenance hemodialysis. Patients on longer duration of dialysis (>5 years) consistently showed lower mean scores across most domains. Statistically significant differences were

observed in physical functioning (p = 0.034), role physical (p = 0.038), role emotional (p = 0.032), social functioning (p = 0.012), and general health perception (p = 0.037).

Table III: Comparison of SF-36 Domain Scores According to Duration of Hemodialysis (n = 100).

SF-36 Domain	3 Months-<1 Year Mean ± SD	1-5 Years Mean ± SD	>5 Years Mean ± SD	p-value
Physical Functioning	56.32 ± 22.42	53.72 ± 23.02	38.70 ± 23.50	0.034
Role Limitations due to Physical Problems	36.92 ± 26.54	28.32 ± 25.93	15.82 ± 27.21	0.038
Role Limitations due to Emotional Problems	52.58 ± 23.98	45.04 ± 23.54	32.83 ± 25.02	0.032
Vitality	44.17 ± 17.35	38.46 ± 17.21	33.14 ± 17.85	0.117
Mental Health	58.40 ± 18.30	50.70 ± 17.50	46.80 ± 19.90	0.085
Social Functioning	44.26 ± 16.04	36.87 ± 15.87	29.24 ± 17.32	0.012
Pain	67.96 ± 22.92	66.94 ± 22.68	61.78 ± 23.28	0.654
General Health Perception	29.28 ± 11.08	26.98 ± 10.96	20.36 ± 12.52	0.037

DISCUSSION

This observational cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Nephrology, Shaheed Suhrawardy Medical College Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh after approval of the study protocol. A total of 100 patients with chronic kidney disease undergoing maintenance hemodialysis were enrolled based on predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria using purposive sampling. The study aimed to assess the impact of hemodialysis duration and clinical factors on health-related quality of life, which was evaluated using the validated Bangla version of the SF-36 questionnaire, with comparison of domain scores across different durations of dialysis.

The present study demonstrated that the majority of CKD patients on maintenance hemodialysis belonged to the older age groups, with the highest proportion in the 61–70 years category (33.0%), and showed a clear male predominance (76.0%). Diabetic nephropathy (32.0%) emerged as the leading cause of CKD, followed by hypertension (23.0%), while most patients exhibited serum creatinine levels between 5–7 mg/dl (42.0%), indicating a considerable burden of advanced renal impairment among the study population. These findings are consistent with Billah et al. who also reported a predominance of patients in the 50–70 year age range (72–73%), with male preponderance, along with diabetic nephropathy as the leading etiological factor and markedly elevated creatinine levels reflecting advanced disease status [13]. Similarly, Biswas et al. observed a middle-aged predominance with a higher proportion of males, and highlighted hypertension (77.1%) and diabetes (52.6%) as major comorbidities contributing to CKD burden, alongside significant metabolic derangements including elevated creatinine levels [14]. Tasnim et al. further reinforced these observations by reporting a predominance of middle-aged male patients with hypertension (73%) and diabetes (36–37%) as leading comorbid conditions, as well as a significant association between CKD and lower socioeconomic and educational status, which further contributes to disease

burden and delayed presentation. In addition [15], Arshad et al. reported that although glomerulonephritis remains an important cause of CKD in Bangladesh (~40%), diabetes (~24–30%) and hypertension (~15–25%) are increasingly significant contributors, particularly among older male populations, reflecting an ongoing epidemiological transition in the etiological profile of CKD [16]. Overall, the present findings are in agreement with existing literature, demonstrating that CKD patients undergoing hemodialysis are predominantly older males with a high burden of diabetic and hypertensive nephropathy, elevated biochemical markers of renal dysfunction, and a substantial cumulative comorbidity profile.

The majority of patients in the present study were receiving maintenance hemodialysis for 1–5 years (56.0%), followed by those on dialysis for less than 1 year (27.0%), while a smaller proportion had a duration exceeding 5 years (17.0%). This distribution indicates that most patients remain within the intermediate dialysis duration category, whereas relatively fewer patients survive into long-term dialysis duration. A similar pattern was reported by Chen et al., who observed that most patients were clustered within the <5-year dialysis duration group, with progressively fewer patients surviving beyond 10–15 years, highlighting the limited proportion of long-term survivors in chronic dialysis populations [17]. Likewise, Konnur et al. reported a comparable trend, where the mean dialysis duration was approximately 2–4 years, with the majority of patients falling within the 1–5 year category and only a smaller fraction surviving beyond 5 years [18]. Overall, these findings are consistent with existing evidence, suggesting that most hemodialysis patients are concentrated in the early to mid-duration stages of treatment, while long-term dialysis survival remains relatively uncommon.

The present study demonstrated markedly impaired health-related quality of life among patients undergoing maintenance hemodialysis, with consistently low SF-36 domain scores across multiple dimensions. The lowest scores were observed

in general health perception (25.54 ± 11.52) and role limitations due to physical problems (27.02 ± 26.56), indicating severe impairment in perceived overall health status and functional capacity. Physical functioning (49.58 ± 22.98), vitality (38.59 ± 17.47), and social functioning (36.79 ± 16.41) were also notably reduced, reflecting significant limitations in daily physical activities and social engagement. In contrast, mental health scores were comparatively higher (51.96 ± 18.56), suggesting partial preservation of psychological well-being despite substantial physical deterioration. A similar pattern was reported by Alam et al., who observed globally reduced SF-36 scores across all domains in hemodialysis patients, with particularly low physical component scores (physical functioning, role physical, and general health markedly reduced), along with reduced vitality and impaired social functioning, while mental health domains were relatively less affected, with an overall mean QoL score of 47.24 ± 11.52 [19]. Likewise, Kuzstal et al. found significantly lower SF-36 scores in dialysis patients compared with healthy controls, with pronounced deficits in physical functioning and role physical domains, as well as reduced vitality and general health perception, whereas mental health scores were comparatively higher than physical domains, although overall quality of life remained substantially impaired [20]. Overall, the present findings are consistent with existing literature, indicating that patients on maintenance hemodialysis experience significant deterioration in physical, functional, and social aspects of quality of life, while psychological domains tend to be relatively less affected.

The present study further demonstrated a clear decline in health-related quality of life with increasing duration of maintenance hemodialysis, with patients receiving dialysis for more than 5 years consistently showing lower SF-36 scores across most domains compared to those with shorter dialysis duration. The most pronounced reductions were observed in physical functioning (56.32 ± 22.42 in 3 months–<1 year vs 38.70 ± 23.50 in >5 years), role limitations due to physical problems (36.92 ± 26.54 vs 15.82 ± 27.21), role limitations due to emotional problems (52.58 ± 23.98 vs 32.83 ± 25.02), social functioning (44.26 ± 16.04 vs 29.24 ± 17.32), and general health perception (29.28 ± 11.08 vs 20.36 ± 12.52), with statistically significant differences observed in these domains ($p = 0.034, 0.038, 0.032, 0.012, \text{ and } 0.037$ respectively). Although mental health (58.40 ± 18.30 vs 46.80 ± 19.90), vitality (44.17 ± 17.35 vs 33.14 ± 17.85), and pain (67.96 ± 22.92 vs 61.78 ± 23.28) also demonstrated a declining trend with increasing dialysis duration, these changes were not statistically significant, suggesting relative preservation of certain psychosocial and symptom-related dimensions. These findings are consistent with Van et al., who reported a progressive decline in physical functioning over time in a large cohort of 714 hemodialysis patients, with longer dialysis exposure and older age strongly associated with worse physical quality of life trajectories [21]. Similarly, Unruh et al. in the HEMO Study demonstrated a gradual decline in SF-36 physical health domains over time, while mental health measures remained relatively stable, highlighting the disproportionate impact of dialysis duration on physical rather than psychological well-being [22]. In addition, Diaz-Buxo et al. reported that patients on longer-term dialysis had consistently lower Physical Functioning, Role Physical, and General Health scores, with comparatively less consistent changes in emotional and mental health domains [23]. Furthermore, Chuasuwana et al. observed across multiple hemodialysis populations that physical domains of

SF-36 were most severely affected, while emotional and mental health measures showed relatively smaller or inconsistent differences across groups [24]. Overall, the present findings align with existing evidence, demonstrating that increasing duration of hemodialysis is associated with a progressive deterioration in physical and social aspects of quality of life, while psychological domains tend to remain relatively preserved.

LIMITATIONS

The study had several limitations:

- The study was conducted in a single tertiary care hospital in Dhaka city; therefore, the findings may not be fully generalizable to the broader population of Bangladesh.
- The study was carried out over a relatively short duration, which may limit the ability to observe long-term trends and outcomes.
- The relatively small sample size may limit the statistical power of the study and the precision of the findings.

CONCLUSION

Chronic kidney disease patients undergoing maintenance hemodialysis represent a clinically vulnerable group with multiple sociodemographic and disease-related challenges. The present study demonstrates that health-related quality of life is significantly impaired across most domains, particularly in physical and general health aspects. Furthermore, increasing duration of hemodialysis is associated with a progressive decline in several quality of life domains, including physical, emotional, social functioning, and overall health perception, indicating that prolonged dialysis exposure has a detrimental impact on patient well-being.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I would like to express my sincere gratitude for the invaluable support and cooperation provided by the staff, participants and my co-authors/colleagues who contributed to this study.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

There are no conflicts of interest.

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